

Teachers in Comfort Support Happiness in Bhutan: A Case of Secondary Schools from Mongar District

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Abstract:- Occupational stress refers to a condition in which all aspects of a person's job interact with him and alter his psychological or physiological state. The term "stress" was coined by Selye (1959) as the "non-specific response of the organism to any demand for change." Organizational health, on the other hand, is ability of an organization to achieve its goals and objectives in relation to its environment, with the goal of improving the organization's performance and supporting the well-being of its personnel. A study investigated the occupational stress of secondary school teachers in Bhutan's Mongar area. It also sought to determine the impact of organizational health on workplace stress. The following hypotheses were formulated: (I) There is no significant difference in occupational stress between secondary school male and female instructors, and (II) there is no significant association between occupational stress and perceived organizational health. Study purposively sampled 100 teachers (50 male and 50 female) from 6 secondary schools of Mongar districts of Bhutan. Published occupational Stress Scale, Organizational Health Description Data collection was done using questionnaire. Statistical methods such as mean, standard deviation, t-test analysis, and correlation coefficient were used to examine the data. Male and female secondary school teachers possess moderate level of occupational stress and in perceived organizational health, they fall on above average category. There exists no significant difference in occupational stress among male and female primary school teachers. There are no significant differences in perceived organization health among the two groups. There is a correlation between occupational stress and reported organizational health among school teachers of secondary level.

Keywords:- Occupational Stress, Organizational Health, Secondary School, Teachers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Every teacher performs several managerial functions in the field of curriculum, planning, resource management, management of examinations, and other pertaining task in school which influence the actual family and social role of the teachers in the school besides teaching[1]. The result of the failure of an organism to react correctly to physical or emotional burdens is termed stress[2]. Organization's ability to achieve its goals based on an environment that seeks to improve organizational performance and support employee well-being is defined as organizational health[3]. In the present study the organizational health refers to the work

environment that prevails in the school which may in turn support to teachers to achieve the goals.

Occupational stress generally arises whenever there is a disparity among the burdens of the job and means and competences of the individual worker to come across those burdens[4]. A teacher is stressed by the performance of a school to survive in its environment and its compatibility, upgrade and expand its ability to adapt more. The different responsibilities shouldered by the teachers in the school cause stress to them as a teacher cannot fulfill his duties neither at home nor in the school[5]. Basic trigger for occupational stress is due to the mixture of stretched occupied hours, inadequate salary, part vagueness, reduced instruction services, absence of public credit, disadvantaged organizational environment, stressed link with colleague, emotional state of being treated falsely, inadequate credit or incentive for a job well completed, absence of job safety, office policies and most essentially, amplified burdens to achieve jobs without enough power and or incomes. This cause them a problem to balance between the job and the family burdens, ultimately suffering from stress in the job having negative impression to their family and individual life. Stress in their day-to-day life will lower psychological wellbeing.

It is very important that the teachers must have sound physical and mental health with less strain, only then the coordination of education can verify to be a suitable for continuance of our society. This study was undertaken to study the occupational stress among schoolteachers of Bhutan in relation to organizational health. The study aimed to help the educational planners to understand psychological orientation of the schoolteachers. Which eventually, will support well management of education functionality in schools and support production of productive citizen for the nation.

II. METHODOLOGY

Bhutan is a peaceful country in South Asia, also known as the Land of the Thunder Dragon. the King promotes democracy in Bhutan constitution is governed by the principle of gross national happiness. Religious citizens of the nation never fail to make a daily impact to support the vision of king and peace of life. Historical and ancient monasteries stand guard of peace and happiness on snow-tipped peaks and lush valleys. This study adopted descriptive survey method to find out the relationship between occupational stresses of the secondary school teachers of Mongar district of Bhutan with their perceived organizational health. Only method to collect opinions,

attitudes, suggestions for improving educational procedures and instructions, and other data is descriptive survey[6].

Study purposively collected data from teachers of 6 secondary schools of Mongar district of Bhutan. As of 2015 statistic, there were 326 Male and 140 Female teachers under Mongar district. This study was conducted on 100 teachers comprising of 50 each male and female secondary school teachers[7]. Study used pre developed occupational stress scale and organizational health tool by experts [8]–[10]. In this scale, occupational stress means a feeling of tension, posed pressure on mind and body and dissatisfaction, which arise due to occupational demands of a person. The feeling of occupational stress for a teacher caused primarily by nine dimensions of occupation like; workload, role ambiguity, groupism and external pressure, responsibility, powerlessness, work relationships, working conditions, personal inadequacy, and lack of motivation. The scale is comprehensive in nature and measures the extent and level of occupational stress among teachers on different dimensions without discriminating male- female

and rural-urban teachers. Organizational health study used organizational health description questionnaire. OHDQ are positive and all scored in the same pattern, giving a weight age to each response ranging from 1 to 5, with 5 indicating complete agreement and 1 indicating disagreement. To collect and carry out the confirmed data, investigator seek out permission and approval from the Director General, Department of School Education and Chief District Education Officer. In the second phase the investigator visited concern secondary school and seek permission from the principals. Then the investigator approached the respondents and the basic concept, items of the questionnaire and the purpose of the research was explained to the respondents. Relevant responses and the information provided by the learners was kept confidential and used only for the purpose of this research work. They were given enough time to think and respond. The filled questionnaires were collected and data was tabulated according to different categories.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Occupational stress of the secondary school teachers

Occupational stress among secondary school teachers was explored by calculating mean and percentage. The mean score of occupational stress for male and female secondary school teachers are 89.08 and 87.26 respectively. (Table 1)

Gender	Meanscore	Corresponding z-score	Level of stress
Male	89.08	-0.36	Moderate
Female	87.26	-0.349	Moderate

Table 1: Level of occupational stress

By referring the test manual, the total mean scores fall under moderate level. This indicates that both the male and female secondary school teachers possess moderate level of occupational stress. They appear to be balanced from professional point of view. They try to manage with stressful situation on their own. They are not reactive about the workplace situation. They are balanced, mutually associative and show concern for each other.

Moreover, the teachers here are neither overloaded with the work assigned to them nor remain idle in the school in academic as well as in non-academic and their works are cordially supported by supervisors. The teachers can priorities job role between teaching and non-teaching work. Supervisor clearly provides the instruction and information regarding the organizational expectations, teachers and students behavior.

The community interference in job role of teacher, making pressurized is moderate and there is no formation of groups among teachers in the working place which would make teaching atmosphere non-conductive. It also indicates that an individual teacher spends significant amount of time interacting with other colleagues, attending meetings and trying to work cooperatively and motivate each other's to meet deadlines and schedules.

The teachers over here believe that the progress, prosperity of the school and development of overall personality of the students are solely responsible to them and the strained relations among colleagues are not there and every teacher enjoy working with each other as a team. Every teacher sense that lack of cooperation among them might lead to poor results.

Teachers here believe in better working environment with designed infrastructure and the employee-oriented attitude of employers. And here the teachers work without tense circumstances and lack of favoritism on the part of authorities. All teachers are treated same.

Teachers were able to keep up to date knowledge in the existing job without affect to physical health and are not worried for the downfall of moral values among students and teachers and the hard work and efficient performance of a teachers are recognized by the administration and authorities. The present job doesn't have the effect on holidays, the salaries and financial benefits doesn't increase their work dissatisfaction.

Level	Percentage wise data on each level of occupational Stress based on gender	
	Male	Female
Extremely high	-	-
High	4%	12 %
Above average	18 %	10 %
Moderate	40 %	32 %
Below average	16 %	14 %
Low	10 %	22 %
Extremely low	12 %	10 %

Table 2: The level of occupational stress in percentage

From Table 2 it has been observed that 4 % of male secondary school teachers have high level of occupational stress, 18 % of above average, 40 % of moderate level, 16 % of below average, 10 % of low and 12 % of extremely low level of occupational stress. Similarly, 12 % of female secondary school teachers have high level of occupational stress, 10 % of above average, 32 % of moderate level, 14 %

of below average, 22 % of low and 10 % of extremely low level of occupational stress.

B. Perceived Organizational health of the secondary school teachers

To explore the level of perceived organizational health of the secondary school teachers, mean and percentage were calculated. Data relating to perceived organizational health is presented in the below given table.

Gender	Task	Dimensionwise Mean score			Total
		Maintenance Needs	Growth Changefulness	and	
Male	48.24	46.34	63.04	157.62	
Female	47.52	45.04	60.66	153.22	

Table 3: Data relating to perceived organizational health of the secondary school teachers

Table 3: shows the data relating to perceived organizational health of the secondary school teachers of Mongar district of Bhutan. A look at the above table reflects that in perceived organizational health, the mean score of the male and female secondary school teachers for task conferred dimensions are 48.24 and 47.52 respectively. By referring to the test manual, the above stated score falls in above average category. This indicates that both the male and female secondary school teachers do possess above average level of perceived organizational health in Task Conferred Dimension. This can further be explained that in task conferred dimension of perceived organizational health the secondary school teachers understand the goals of the organization and accept them as realistic ends. It reflects that information and communication within the organization travel reasonably well which enable the organization to sense internal strain and conflict that is promptly dealt with them. The distribution of power and influence is equitable. Referring to maintenance needs dimension of perceived organization health, it is observed that the mean scores of the male and female secondary school teachers are 46.34 and 45.04 respectively, which fall in above average category. This indicates that both themale and female secondary school teachers do possess above average level of perceived organizational health in Maintenance Needs dimension. They use their resources, especially their personnel, effectively.

want to stay. They are pleased to be a part of the organization and are delighted to be a part of it. Referring to growth and changefulness dimension of perceived organizational health, it is observed that the mean scores of the male and female secondary school teachers are 63.04 and 60.66 respectively, which fall in above average category. This indicates both male and female secondary school teachers do possess above average level of perceived organizational health in growth and changefulness dimension. When confronted with obstacles, organizations design new procedures that allow them to progress toward new goals, produce new goods, and diversify their operations. Rather than being dignified and conventional, such systems evolve, develop, and alter. Referring to the total mean scores of male and female secondary school teachers for perceived organizational health it shows 157.62 and 153.22 respectively. By referring to the test manual, the above score falls in above average category. This indicates that the secondary school teachers, both male and female do possess above average level of perceived organizational health. This can further be explained that the school as an organization under which teachers work are able to create and maintain a healthy working environment for faculty members, staff and students. Teachers here become aware of an organization and they know the shortcomings, management weaknesses and necessary thinking skills so that they make important steps to enhance organizational health by employing efficient individuals, making connections and benefitting from information, supporting innovations and creativity, establishing training courses and encouraging organizational culture and participation to execute their functions effectively, operate and achieve their targets successfully.

Internal tension is modest; people are neither overworked nor idle. The individuals' personal needs and the organization's role responsibilities are well aligned. They enjoy their work and believe that they are learning and improving as they contribute to the company. They are drawn to the organization, take pride in belonging to it, and

Level	Male	Female
Low	-	-
Average	6%	8%
Above average	48 %	52 %
High	46 %	40 %

Table 4: Level of perceived organizational health in percentage

From the table 3.2.2 it has been observed that 6 % of male secondary school teachers have average perceived organizational health, 48% of above average and 46% of high perceived organizational health. Whereas female

secondary school teachers have 8% of average perceived organizational health, 52 % of above average and 40 % of high perceived organizational health.

C. Gender wise variation in occupational stress secondary school teachers

Gender	N	Mean Score	SD	SEd	df	t-value	Level of significant	
							0.01	0.05
Male	50	89.08	18.629					
Female	50	87.26	20.147	3.881	98	.469	N.S	N.S

Table 5: Occupational stress among secondary school teachers based on gender

N.S = Not Significant

The table 5 depicts the mean score, SD, SEd, df and the t-value of secondary school teachers in occupational stress. Referring to above given table, it is observed that the mean score of the male and female secondary school teachers of Mongar districts are 89.08 and 87.26 respectively. Similarly, the SD's are 18.629 and 20.147 respectively. The Standard error of difference (SEd) is 3.881. The calculated t-value is .469. Referring to 98 degree of freedom (df), the tabulated value at 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance are 2.63 and 1.98 respectively. This indicates that the calculated t-value of occupational stress among secondary male and female teachers are less than tabulated t-value at both 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance. It reflects that both male and female secondary school teachers do not differ significantly in occupational stress. Based on the above findings it can be stated that the hypothesis; i.e.;

“there exists no significant difference among secondary school male and female teachers of Mongar district of Bhutan in their occupational stress” is thus accepted.

D. Difference in perceived organizational health among male and female secondary school teachers

The table 6 depicts the mean score, SD, SEd, df and the t-value of secondary school teachers in perceived organizational health. Referring to above given table, it is observed that the mean score of the male and female secondary school teachers of Mongar districts are 157.62 and 153.22 respectively. Similarly the SD's are 23.543 and 26.620 respectively. The Standard error of difference (SEd) is 5.026. The calculated t-value is .875. Referring to 98 degree of freedom (df), the tabulated value at 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance are 2.63 and 1.98 respectively.

Gender	N	MeanScore	SD	SEd	df	t-value	Level of significant	
							0.01	0.05
Male	50	157.62	23.543					
Female	50	153.22	26.620	5.026	98	.875	N.S	N.S

Table 6: Group difference among secondary school teachers based on gender in perceived organizational health

NS= Not Significant

This indicates that the calculated t-value of perceived organizational health among secondary male and female teachers are less than tabulated t-value at both 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance. It reflects that both male and female secondary school teachers do not differ significantly in perceived organizational health. Based on the above findings it can be stated that the hypothesis no.2; i.e.; “there exists no significant difference among secondary school male and female teachers of Mongar district of Bhutan in their perceived organizational health” is thus accepted.

E. Relationship between Occupational stress and perceived Organizational health of secondary school teachers

The table depicts the mean score, SD, df, t- value and coefficient correlation of secondary school teachers in occupational stress and perceived organizational health. Referring to above given table, it is observed that the mean score of the male and female secondary school teachers of Mongar district are 88.17 and 155.42 respectively. Similarly, the SD's are 19.327 and 25.099 respectively. The value of coefficient of correlation is 0.464. Referring to 198 degree of freedom (df), the tabulated value at 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance are 0.181 and 0.138 respectively.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	df	Co-efficient of correlation	Level of significant
Dependent Occupational stress	100	88.17	19.327			0.01 0.05
Independent Organizational health	100	155.42	25.099	198	0.464	.181 .138

Table 7: Result pertaining to the relation between occupational stress and perceived organizational health of secondary school teachers

This indicates that the calculated co-efficient of correlation of an occupational stress and perceived organizational health among secondary male and female teachers are more than tabulated co-efficient of correlation at both 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance. Referring to above given table, it is observed that the value of co-efficient of correlation comes out to be at moderate level indicating that there is positive correlation between occupational stress and perceived organizational health of secondary school teachers. Based on the above data it can be stated that the hypothesis no.3; i.e.; “there exists no significant relationship between occupational stress and perceived organizational health of the secondary school teachers of Mongar district of Bhutan” is thus rejected.

IV. CONCLUSION

Teachers believe in better working environment with designed infrastructure and employee-oriented attitude of employers. Both male and female secondary school teachers possess moderate level of occupational stress. They are balanced, mutually associative and show concern for each other. All teachers are treated same by the administrative. Teachers from Mongar district perceived organizational health above average level. The school as an organization under which teachers work are able to create and maintain a healthy working environment. Teachers become aware of an organization, and they know the shortcomings, management of weaknesses and necessary thinking skills. Both male and female secondary school teachers do not differ significantly in occupational stress. Both male and female secondary school teachers do not perceive significantly different in organizational health. There exists positive relationship between occupational stress and perceived organizational health of the secondary school teachers of Mongar district of Bhutan.

Further study should be conducted on a larger scale incorporating larger sample size. A larger sample with more schools and teachers would be important to validate these findings across urban, suburban and rural communities. The Private and Government teachers teaching at primary and tertiary level could be taken along with their seniority in service and age, their qualification and salary. Other variables like organizational commitment, achievement motivation, locus of control and decision making style of principal could be used to relate to occupational stress.

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